

Chronic Cutaneous-Visceral Leishmaniasis: A Forgotten Differential Diagnosis

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ABSTRACT

Leishmaniasis is a vector-borne disease. Three types of manifestations are recognized in the literature: Cutaneous, Mucocutaneous, and Visceral. The transmission and infection mechanism begins when the sandfly feeds on blood and regurgitates promastigotes into the skin, which are phagocytosed by macrophages. The diagnosis is based on clinical features and laboratory tests, such as direct parasitological examination, to increase diagnostic accuracy. Regarding the first case of Visceral Leishmaniasis in the state of Guerrero. An 18-year-old man with unspecified dermatitis since the age of 8, which began with an unquantified, intermittent fever, predominantly in the evening. On the fourth day, the patient presented edema in the auricles, itching, erythema, and increased local temperature that evolved into a papule and blister, with the formation of an indurated scab that, when detached, leaves an ulcer. This invades subcutaneous cellular tissue and disappears after 6 weeks, leaving an atrophic scar. This scar has occurred at least 6 times a year for 9 years, alternating between the auricles, elbows, and ankles. The patient therefore came for medical evaluation with an ulcer on the inner side and upper third of the left leg with an increase in diameter, edema, and a necrotic ulcer with purulent and foul-smelling discharge. A wound smear was requested, which was stained with Giemsa and found *Leishmania* spp. PCR with specific oligonucleotides: Mexican visceral *Leishmania*. After confirming the diagnosis of the disseminated mucocutaneous variant, it was decided to initiate systemic and local intralesional treatment with systemic antimonial. During follow-up, the patient observed scleroatrophic healing of previously ulcerated lesions, with no signs of infection or new lesions. It is important to understand leishmaniasis as a differential diagnosis for ulcerated lesions of variable distribution with a short or chronic course, and to perform the necessary studies to achieve appropriate treatment and improve the patient's prognosis.

KEYWORDS: Leishmaniasis, skin disease, Phlebotomus Fever

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
02 October 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

INTRODUCTION

Leishmaniasis is a vector-borne disease, specifically protozoa of the genus *Leishmania*, transmitted through the bite of flies (*Phlebotomus* or *Lutzomyia*). It causes a wide range of clinical manifestations. Three types of manifestations are recognized in the literature: cutaneous, mucocutaneous, and visceral.(1) The WHO has designated leishmaniasis as a neglected tropical disease.(4) In Mexico, four species of *Leishmania* are recognized, including *Leishmania mexicana* in Campeche, Oaxaca, and Quintana Roo, *Leishmania*

infantum in Veracruz, and *Leishmania braziliensis* in Campeche, according to data published through 2020. The regional incidence rate in the Americas is 18.37 cases per 100,000 inhabitants. Mexico showed a reduction in the number of cases per 100,000 (5.81), representing a 56% decrease in incidence. In Mexico, the states with the highest transmission are Tabasco and Yucatán. (2)

The transmission and infection mechanism begins when the sandfly feeds on blood and regurgitates promastigotes into the skin, which are phagocytosed by macrophages. These

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promastigotes transform into amastigotes within the macrophage. At this point, they multiply in cells, including macrophages, in various tissues, causing the infection. (3)

There are several clinical forms of leishmaniasis, which depend on the species of *Leishmania* involved and the host's immune response. The clinical manifestations of the visceral presentation are persistent fever, splenomegaly, hepatomegaly, hypergammaglobulinemia, and weight loss. In its cutaneous and mucocutaneous presentation, the manifestations are mainly aesthetic, characteristically a papule that lasts for weeks or months at the site of the sandfly bite. This enlarges until it becomes a nodule that slowly ulcerates over the following months and finally forms hyperkeratotic plaques or verrucous membranes. (3)(4)

The diagnosis is based on clinical features and laboratory tests to increase diagnostic accuracy, such as direct parasitological examination (microscopy, histopathology, and parasite culture) and indirect serological and molecular diagnostic tests such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR). (4)(5)

In MCL, the otorhinolaryngological tract, mucosal tissue, and cartilage are affected. Direct diagnostic tests such as light microscopy can help establish a more precise diagnosis and

facilitate clinical management. (6) Regarding the first case of visceral leishmaniasis in the state of Guerrero, which is characterized.

CLINICAL CASE

An 18-year-old man originally from and residing in Acapulco, Guerrero, had a history of unspecified dermatitis since the age of 8. The dermatitis began with an unmeasured, intermittent fever, predominantly in the evening. On the fourth day, he presented with edema in the auricles, pruritus, erythema, and localized fever that evolved into a papule and blister. On the seventh day, he presented with the formation of an indurated scab that, upon detachment, left an ulcer. This crust invaded subcutaneous tissue and disappeared within 6 weeks, leaving an atrophic scar. The condition had occurred at least 6 times a year for 9 years, alternating between the auricles, elbows, and ankles. He presented to our hospital 6 months earlier with an ulcer on the inner surface and upper third of his left leg, increasing in diameter, edema, and a necrotic ulcer with purulent and foul-smelling discharge. Elephantiasis and lymphangitis are included as diagnostic possibilities, as well as coexistence of infection in ulcerated lesions.

Image 1.

A) Anterior aspect of the left leg with an extensive ulcer with irregular borders, the base covered by necrotic material with macerated, purplish tissue, adipose tissue, thick crusts, hemorrhagic areas, and signs of possible secondary infection. B) Left foot, lateral view. Infiltrated, fibrous, ulcerated plaque on the lateral side of the foot, with crusted and erythematous areas, partial ulceration with irregular borders, in the context of thickened skin. C and D) Cartilaginous lesion with bilateral thickening of the auricles, with apparent dermal infiltration and erythematous nodules, without ulceration. E) Posterior lesion on the right arm, skin with thickening with a lichenoid or scleroatrophic appearance, and irregular pigmentation.

He was admitted to the emergency room where he was evaluated by Internal Medicine for soft tissue sepsis. He was found to have jaundice, a dermal lesion primarily on the anterior region of his left leg, a large ulcer measuring 25 x 10 cm with irregular borders, its base covered by necrotic material with macerated and purplish tissue, with the presence of adipose tissue, thick scabs, hemorrhagic areas, and signs of possible secondary infection due to perilesional erythema. Various dermal lesions of variable distribution were observed, mainly on the elbows and ears, with irregular borders and a scleroatrophic appearance. Labs are extended with the following results: Erythrocytes 2.38×10^6 , Hemoglobin 5.3 g/dL, Hematocrit 17.1%, MCV 71.8 fL, HbMC 22.3 g/dL, Platelets 94×10^3 , Leukocytes 2.0×10^3 ,

Neutrophils 1.2×10^3 , Lymphocytes 0.3×10^3 , Monocytes 0.5×10^3 , PT 16.3 sec, PTT 44.4 sec, Glucose 113 mg/dL, Creatinine 0.51 mg/dL, Albumin 1.39, GGT 109 IU/L, LDH 1083.0, AP 324.42 IU/L. The differential diagnosis included skin lesions due to vasculitis, so antinuclear antibodies were ordered, which were negative. P-ANCA and C-ANCA were also negative. Lepromatous skin lesions were also ordered, although these were not characteristic of leprosy.

An upper abdominal ultrasound was ordered, which revealed hepatomegaly and splenomegaly, pericholesic edema, bilateral pleural effusion, and ascites. An echocardiogram revealed right ventricular dilation and mild tricuspid regurgitation secondary to annular dilation. Within the diagnostic approach, when integrating clinical data and its evolution, a vector-borne disease is suspected. Relevant

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clinical data include hepatomegaly, splenomegaly, fever with a variant pattern, pancytopenia, dermal lesions that initially appear as a papule and subsequently evolve into a nodule, and finally hyperkeratotic or verrucous ulcers of variable distribution and size, including cartilaginous lesions in the auricles. Therefore, a wound smear was requested, which was stained with Giemsa and found *Leishmania* spp. PCR with specific oligonucleotides: Mexican visceral *Leishmania*. After confirming the diagnosis of the disseminated mucocutaneous variant, it was decided to initiate systemic and local intralesional treatment with systemic antimonial at 20 mg/kg/day for 20 days. In the left leg lesion, it was decided to attempt intralesional infiltration of 5 ml for 7 days. Due to infected ulcerated lesions, it was decided to continue antimicrobial treatment with fourth-generation cephalosporins for 7 days. Regarding visceral involvement, determined by the presence of hepatomegaly and splenomegaly, perivesicular edema, bilateral pleural effusion, and ascites, it was decided to use liposomal amphotericin B at a cumulative dose of 18 mg/kg.

The patient was scheduled for follow-up visits at 1, 3, and 6 months. Scleroatrophic healing of previously ulcerated lesions was observed, with no signs of infection or new lesions.

DISCUSSION

Leishmaniasis infection primarily affects low-income individuals with limited access to health services. In Mexico, it constitutes a public health problem due to its incidence, morbidity, wide geographic distribution, and the variety of parasite species. (1) We present the case of infection with visceral *Leishmania mexicana*. Diagnosis of cutaneous leishmaniasis begins with clinical suspicion and epidemiology corresponding to endemic areas. Clinical suspicion is presented with chronic, nonhealing skin lesions, usually in exposed areas, with the typical course of papules, nodules, ulcers, and plaques. (7) To determine the diagnosis, confirmation of the *Leishmania* parasite or its DNA in the lesioned tissue is necessary. This includes direct microscopic examination, parasitological culture, histopathology, polymerase chain reaction (PCR), which is considered the most sensitive and specific, and immunohistochemical tests. (7)(8) Regarding the diagnostic method used, histopathology was decided upon, which consists of demonstrating by taking a skin biopsy and demonstrating granulomatous dermatitis with parasitized macrophages. Given the difficulty in observing the parasite, there are special stains that support its visualization, such as Giemsa, PAS, silver and methenamine, increasing the sensitivity of the test. Subsequently, molecular diagnosis is performed with polymerase chain reaction, which is a sensitive and specific method for the detection of *Leishmania* DNA in tissue samples and allows the species to be identified, which is considered important for treatment and possible prognosis. It is performed by biopsy, lesion scraping, or even blood in some cases. (10). Regarding treatment, it is

divided into 2 entities since it has visceral as well as cutaneous damage. Regarding the treatment of the visceral component, liposomal amphotericin (L-AmB) is recommended due to its safety profile as well as effectiveness compared to other types of amphotericin B, with a recommended cumulative dose of 18-21 mg/kg. (11)(12) Regarding the cutaneous component, the use of intralesional antimonials is recommended to limit the extension of lesions as well as their dissemination.

CONCLUSION

Leishmania infection is still a common diagnosis in areas of Latin America. In the state of Guerrero, Mexico, there are no reports of additional *Leishmania* cases. However, the state of Guerrero is recognized as a geographic location where infection is possible due to its climate, socioeconomic status, and general hygiene conditions. It is important to understand leishmaniasis as a differential diagnosis for ulcerated lesions of variable distribution with a short or chronic course, and to conduct the necessary studies to achieve appropriate treatment and improve the patient's prognosis.

REFERENCES

- I. Gurel MS, Tekin B, Uzun S. Cutaneous leishmaniasis: A great imitator. *Clin Dermatol*. 2020;38(2):140–51.
- II. National Center for Disease Prevention and Control (CENAPRECE). Guidelines for the Medical Care of Leishmaniasis in Mexico [Internet]. Mexico: Ministry of Health; 2022.
- III. Burza S, Croft SL, Boelaert M. Leishmaniasis. *Lancet* [Internet]. 2018;392(10151):951–70.
- IV. de Vries HJC, Schallig HD. Cutaneous leishmaniasis: A 2022 updated narrative review into diagnosis and management developments. *Am J Clin Dermatol* [Internet]. 2022;23(6):823–40.
- V. Goto H, Lindoso JAL. Current diagnosis and treatment of cutaneous and mucocutaneous leishmaniasis. *Expert Rev Anti Infect Ther* [Internet]. 2010;8(4):419–33.
- VI. Croft SL, Sundar S, Fairlamb AH. Drug resistance in leishmaniasis. *Clin Microbiol Rev* [Internet]. 2006;19(1):111–26.
- VII. Aronson N, Herwaldt BL, Libman M, Pearson R, Lopez-Velez R, Weina P, et al. Diagnosis and treatment of leishmaniasis: Clinical practice guidelines by the infectious diseases society of America (IDSA) and the American society of tropical medicine and hygiene (ASTMH). *Clin Infect Dis* [Internet]. 2016;63(12):1539–57.
- VIII. Graziano T, Ferdock AJ, Rossi CM, Schultz KL. A case of cutaneous leishmaniasis with mucosal involvement in the northern United States. *J Emerg Med* [Internet]. 2024;66(6):e690–3.

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- IX. Taxy JB, Goldin HM, Dickie S, Cibull T. Cutaneous leishmaniasis: Contribution of routine histopathology in unexpected encounters. *Am J Surg Pathol* [Internet]. 2019;43(2):195–200.
- X. Neitzke-Abreu HC, Venazzi MS, Bernal MVZ, Reinhold-Castro KR, Vagetti F, Mota CA, et al. Leishmania (Viannia) DNA detection: accuracy of polymerase chain reaction for the diagnosis of cutaneous leishmaniasis. *PLoS One* [Internet]. 2013;8(7):e62473.
- XI. Chakravarty J, Sundar S. Current and emerging medications for the treatment of leishmaniasis. *Expert Opinion Pharmacother* [Internet]. 2019;20(10):1251–65.
- XII. Alves F, Bilbe G, Blesson S, Goyal V, Monnerat S, Mowbray C, et al. Recent development of treatments for visceral leishmaniasis: Successes, challenges, and prospects. *Clin Microbiol Rev* [Internet]. 2018;31(4).
- XIII. Handler MZ, Patel PA, Kapila R, Al-Qubati Y, Schwartz RA. Cutaneous and mucocutaneous leishmaniasis. *J Am Acad Dermatol* [Internet]. 2015;73(6):911–26.